

Studies on the Continuous Phase in the Vicinity of Emulsion-Droplets. Part III : Continuous Phase Bound to Creamed Droplets

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Various oil-in-water emulsions of different phase-volume ratio ϕ , stabilised by Na-oleate, were prepared and allowed to cream under identical conditions. The cream porosity P and the cream thickness h_c were determined in each case. The values of P , h_c and ϕ were fitted in an empirical equation with constants P' and k . The effects of emulsifier concentration and the nature of the dispersed phase were studied on these constants. Finally, the values of P' were used to calculate $(r_s \text{ cream}/r_d)_{(h_c \phi) \rightarrow 0}$ which is the ratio of the co-sphere radius to the radius of the corresponding droplet closely packed in an emulsion cream in the limiting case when the effect of droplet deformation due to cream thickness as well as that of size variation on P is insignificant.

WHEN two emulsion droplets approach each other, a thin liquid lamella is formed between them. van den Tempel¹ measured the thickness of aqueous lamella between oil drops which were pushed together with a known hydrostatic pressure and observed the stable equilibrium lamellae of thickness ranging from 220 to 100 Å for the systems studied. Sonntag and co-workers² investigated the dynamics of thinning of oil/water/oil and water/oil/water lamella ranging in thickness from 100-1000 Å for selected water-oil systems using micro reflectivity technique and capacity measurements. When non-ionic surfactant was used, the equilibrium aqueous lamellae thickness ranged from 870-85 Å as the KCl concentration in the systems, studied by them, was increased from 10^{-3} to $2N$. To explain the existence of such lamellae Derjaguin introduced the possibility of an additional force acting at right angles to the plain of the liquid film and termed it 'disjoining pressure'³. This became necessary because the hydrostatic forces and invariant surface tension are not sufficient to explain the formation of such liquid lamella. The disjoining pressure responsible for the non-contact of approaching emulsion droplets probably originates in the molecules of the continuous phase bound to them and depends on the thickness of the intervening liquid lamella formed.

Thus the volume of bound continuous phase in an assembly of closely packed emulsion droplets is of considerable importance. As an emulsion cream is a suitable system of closely packed emulsified droplets and the bound continuous phase must reflect its effect on the cream volume, it would be of interest

to measure the cream porosity and to study the effects of some emulsion parameters on it. With this end in view different oil-in-water emulsions were prepared, the cream porosity in each case was determined and the effects of emulsifier concentration and phase-volume ratio were studied.

Experimental

Materials : Benzene and toluene used as disperse phases were B.D.H. (India) products, *o*-xylene, *m*-xylene and *p*-xylene used as disperse phases were products of E. Merck (Germany). Na-oleate used as emulsifier was B.D.H. (England) product. The continuous phase in each case was double distilled conductivity water.

Preparation of Emulsions : Different oil-in-water emulsions were prepared by the method reported earlier⁴.

Procedure : Each emulsion prepared as above at $30^\circ \pm 0.2^\circ$ was allowed to cream up in a graduated glass jar kept in water bath at the same temperature. The rising interface due to separating cream became distinct after a few minutes and its height L from the bottom of the jar was noted at different time intervals t . The height L' of the interface from the bottom after infinite time was determined from the intercept on $\log L$ versus $1/t$ plot which was linear⁴⁻⁵. Again the height H of the top level of cream from the bottom of the jar was determined from the knowledge of the total emulsion volume and the area of cross section A of the jar. The difference $(H-L')$ gave the cream thickness h_c . Further, the emulsifier concentration C was always expressed in gms of Na-oleate per 100 ml of emulsion.

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Results and Discussion

The cream porosity P for each emulsion was calculated using the relation

$$P = \frac{V_c - V_d}{V_c} \quad (1)$$

where V_c is the cream volume and equals Ah_c while V_d is the volume of the disperse phase present in V_c . As the solubility of the disperse phase in the continuous phase is insignificant and V_c is the cream volume at infinite time of creaming it was assumed that no emulsion droplet remained uncreamed and V_d is equal to the volume of the disperse phase in the total emulsion taken.

From a close observation of the values of P , h_c and the phase-volume ratio ϕ , it became apparent that P decreased with increasing ϕ and h_c for emulsions having the same constituents, the same C and prepared under identical conditions. Also, the decrease in P was rapid for smaller values of ϕ and h_c but progressively became slower as ϕ and h_c both increased. In order to find a relation between P , h_c and ϕ the values of P were, therefore, plotted against the product $(h_c \phi)$ for constant C and constant temperature for each system and from the nature of the curve, the data was fitted in the following equation

$$P = P' e^{-kh_c \phi} \quad (2)$$

where P' and k are constants. P' equals P when $(h_c \phi)$ is zero and is a dimensionless quantity while k is the logarithm of the ratio P'/P , when the product $(h_c \phi)$ is unity, and its dimension is cm^{-1} . The values of P' and k were determined from the intercept and the slope respectively of the plot of $\log P$ versus $h_c \phi$ which was linear in each case (Figure 1A to E). The values of P' and k as determined are included in Table 1.

TABLE 1—VALUES OF P' AND k FOR DIFFERENT EMULSION SYSTEMS AT VARYING NA-OLEATE CONCENTRATIONS

Sl. No.	System	Temp. $30^\circ \pm 0.2^\circ$		
		C	P'	k
1.	Benzene/Water	1.0	28.510	0.50063
		1.5	28.840	0.46060
		2.0	29.512	0.39705
2.	Toluene/Water	1.0	28.510	0.41124
		1.5	28.840	0.35983
		2.0	29.174	0.29526
3.	<i>o</i> -Xylene/Water	1.0	28.184	0.35983
		1.5	28.510	0.31986
		2.0	29.174	0.28085
4.	<i>m</i> -Xylene/Water	1.0	28.184	0.31121
		1.5	28.510	0.25588
		2.0	28.840	0.21323
5.	<i>p</i> -Xylene/Water	1.0	28.840	0.38383
		1.5	29.174	0.33866
		2.0	29.512	0.30302

Fig. 1. Plot of $\log P$ versus $h_c \phi$ at $30^\circ \pm 0.2^\circ$ for (A) Benzene/Water, (B) Toluene/Water, (C) *o*-Xylene/water, (D) *m*-Xylene/Water and (E) *p*-Xylene/Water emulsions stabilised by (a) 1% Na-oleate, (b) 1.5% Na-oleate and (c) 2% Na-oleate.

From the above table, it is apparent that P' increases very slowly with C but in view of the data fluctuations involved in such experiments, the variation in P' may be considered as insignificant for the range of C investigated. On the other hand, the decrease in k is distinct as C increases.

Had the droplets in emulsion creams been perfect rigid as well as uniform spheres and capable of

touching each other with hexagonal close packing⁶, P would have been equal to 0.26 and would have remained unaffected with the changes in h_c and ϕ . But these droplets undergo deformation due to multilayer stacking, have size variations and allow a thin lamella of continuous phase to exist between them when packed and as such P will differ from 0.26. The difference ($P-0.26$) will, then, be equal to the algebraic sum of P_d , P_s and P_l which may be defined as the contribution towards P by droplet deformation due to multilayer stacking, size variation and lamellae formation respectively.

P_d will decrease with h_c provided the characteristics of the emulsifier film around the droplets do not change or in other words, C and ϕ are kept constant, because lower h_c will mean decreased stacking resulting in lower static pressure and ultimately causing lesser deformation. It will also decrease with ϕ when C and h_c remain constant because in that case the rigidity of the emulsifier film on the droplet surface will increase making it less deformable. Here it may be pointed out that h_c can be kept constant by suitably changing the geometry of the container in which the creaming occurs or by changing the total volume of the emulsion to be creamed even when ϕ changes. Thus P_d , as defined earlier, will be a function of the product ($h_c\phi$) at constant C such that $P_d = 0$ when ($h_c\phi$) $\rightarrow 0$. For the emulsion cream to be real in this limiting case, h_c and ϕ both should separately decrease and tend to zero till a pair of close packed droplets form the emulsion cream under experimental conditions of creaming. However, if h_c and ϕ actually become zero, the physical significance of emulsion cream will disappear. Further, as the droplet deformation will result in smaller voids giving lower value of P , P_d is a negative quantity.

Similar to P_d , P_s will also decrease with product ($h_c\phi$) at constant C because the decrease in h_c will lead to less voids resulting from the packing of the larger droplets and will thus decrease the probability of smaller droplets to get packed in them and at the same time the decreased ϕ , at constant C , will lead to less size variation and hence less P_s . In the limiting case when ($h_c\phi$) $\rightarrow 0$ and the emulsion cream consists of a pair of close packed droplets, $P_s = 0$. The effect of P_s is to reduce the voids resulting in lower P , therefore, P_s is a negative quantity.

On the other hand, P_l will depend on Δr , where $2\Delta r$ is the thickness of the liquid lamellae intervening the close packed droplets in the emulsion cream. Contrary to P_d and P_s , $P_l \neq 0$ for ($h_c\phi$) $\rightarrow 0$ because $\Delta r \neq 0$ for this limiting case. As the net effect of the liquid lamellae is to increase the void between a pair of droplets in emulsion cream giving higher porosity, P_l is a positive quantity.

In view of the above discussions, and remembering that the contributions P_d and P_s are negative and P_l is positive, we have

$$(P-0.26) = P_l - (P_d + P_s) \quad (3)$$

Here if we assume a co-sphere of radius r_s cream equal to $r_d + \Delta r$ around each closely packed droplet of average radius r_d in the emulsion cream, then the annular space between the droplet and its co-sphere contains only the emulsifier film and the continuous phase molecules which are bound to it and cannot, therefore, be easily dislodged. Such co-spheres can touch each other without overlapping because $2\Delta r$ is the equilibrium thickness of the liquid lamellae and coalescence is insignificant. If we further assume that these co-spheres are hexagonally close packed⁶ then the cream volume V_c is given by

$$V_c = 4/3\pi n r_s^3 \text{ cream} \times 100/74 \quad (4)$$

where n is the total number of such co-spheres in V_c . Further, the total volume occupied by the emulsifier film and rigidly bound continuous phase V_l is given by

$$V_l = 4/3\pi n [r_s^3 \text{ cream} - r_d^3] \quad (5)$$

As P_l can be equated to V_l/V_c , we have from equations (3), (4) and (5)

$$(P-0.26) = [1 - (r_d/r_s \text{ cream})^3]0.74 - (P_d + P_s) \quad (6)$$

Putting the condition ($h_c\phi$) $\rightarrow 0$ and recalling that $P_{(h_c\phi) \rightarrow 0} \simeq P'$ from equation (2) and $(P_d)_{(h_c\phi) \rightarrow 0} = 0$ as well as $(P_s)_{(h_c\phi) \rightarrow 0} = 0$ as discussed earlier, we have from equation (6)

$$(r_s \text{ cream}/r_d)_{(h_c\phi) \rightarrow 0} = \left[\frac{0.74}{(1-P')} \right]^{1/3} \quad (7)$$

Substituting the values of P' from Table 1 the ratio $(r_s \text{ cream}/r_d)_{(h_c\phi) \rightarrow 0}$ were calculated for the creams obtained under the experimental conditions of creaming from the emulsions studied and are tabulated in Table 2.

TABLE 2—VALUES OF $(r_s \text{ cream}/r_d)_{(h_c\phi) \rightarrow 0}$ FOR CREAMS OF DIFFERENT EMULSION SYSTEMS AT VARYING NA-OLEATE CONCENTRATIONS

Temp. 30° ± 0.2°			
Sl. No.	System	C	$(r_s \text{ cream}/r_d)_{(h_c\phi) \rightarrow 0}$
1.	Benzene/Water	1.0	1.0116
		1.5	1.0131
		2.0	1.0162
2.	Toluene/Water	1.0	1.0116
		1.5	1.0131
		2.0	1.0147
3.	<i>o</i> -Xylene/Water	1.0	1.0100
		1.5	1.0116
		2.0	1.0147
4.	<i>m</i> -Xylene/Water	1.0	1.0100
		1.5	1.0116
		2.0	1.0131
5.	<i>p</i> -Xylene/Water	1.0	1.0131
		1.5	1.0147
		2.0	1.0162

From Table 2 it is apparent that the values of $(r_s \text{ cream}/r_d)(h_c\phi) \rightarrow 0$ and hence the volume of the bound continuous phase increases slowly with C for the emulsion systems studied under the conditions of present investigation. They also change with the change of disperse phase if other emulsion parameters remain constant. Similar observations were made earlier by the authors regarding the effects of C and the nature of disperse phase on the ratio of the radius of co-sphere and the radius of the corresponding droplet (r_s/r_d) for dilute emulsions, or un-packed emulsions, in contrast to emulsion cream which may be considered as a close packed emulsion. The variation in $(r_s \text{ cream}/r_d)(h_c\phi) \rightarrow 0$ with C and the nature of disperse phase is the consequence of the variation in distribution of the emulsifier in the interfacial film, disperse phase and the continuous phase when C and the nature of disperse phase are changed either individually or both. This indicates that the effects of C and the nature of disperse phase extend to a considerable distance from the droplet surfaces and immobilise the continuous phase in the vicinity of the droplets. This is in agreement with the view held by Derjaguin⁷ who obtained other evidences for the influence of hydrophilic surfaces

on the structure of water extending to several hundred angstroms from the interface.

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